

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

GA based on the: Erasmus Lump Sum MGA — Multi & Mono - 1.null

PreMETS

**Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System:
An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training**

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

Project Title: **Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training**

Project Number: **101108469**

Topic: **ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP**

Type of Action: **ERASMUS-LS**

D6.3 External Evaluation Strategy

Final

Deliverable:	D6.3 External Evaluation Strategy
Work Package:	WP6: Monitoring and evaluation
Due Date:	M6
Submission Date:	29/12/2023
Start Date of Project:	01/07/2023
Duration of Project:	36 Months
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	CERTH
Version:	1.2
Status:	Final
Author name(s):	Konstantinos Karampourniotis (Living Prospects), Ioanna Tzanavari (Living Prospects), Afroditi Anagnostopoulou (CERTH), Attila Akac (CERTH)
Reviewer(s):	Adrian Solomon (HELIXCONNECT), Giorgios Ntanis (UPRC)
Nature:	✓ R – Report P – Prototype D – Demonstrator O - Other
Dissemination level:	✓ PU – Public CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments
1.0	19/12/2023	Konstantinos Karampourniotis & Ioanna Tzanavari (Living Prospects)	
1.1	27/12/2023	Adrian Solomon (HELIX CONNECT), Giorgios Ntanis (UPRC)	Minor comments and revision
1.2	28/12/2023	Afroditi Anagnostopoulou (CERTH), Attila Akac (CERTH)	Revised final version

Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Monitoring and Evaluation Approaches.....	10
2.1 Results-oriented approach	11
2.2 Participatory approach.....	11
2.3 Theory-based evaluation approach.....	12
2.4 M&E for learning approach.....	13
2.5 Case study evaluation approach	14
2.6 Impact Evaluation approach.....	14
3. Evaluation Strategy	18
3.1 Evaluation Approach	18
3.2 Evaluation Criteria.....	23
3.3 Key Performance Indicators	33
3.4 Work Package Analysis.....	37
3.4.1 WP1: Project management and coordination.....	37
3.4.2 WP2: Predictive manufacturing training content development.....	38
3.4.3 WP3: Micro credential certification framework	39
3.4.4 WP4: PreMETS Predictive Manufacturing Platform.....	40
3.4.5 WP5: Work-based learning pilots.....	41
3.4.6 WP6: Monitoring and evaluation	42
3.4.7 WP7: Impact, Dissemination & Exploitation	43
4. Conclusions.....	46
5. References.....	48
ANNEX A: LIST OF INDICATORS AND PRIORITY LEVEL PER WP	50
ANNEX B: INTERNAL REPORTS' CODIFICATION	52

Tables

Table 1: Monitoring and evaluation approaches.....	15
Table 2: Challenges of evaluation criteria (Source: OECD)	29
Table 3: List of indicators and target values.	35

Figures

Figure 1 – The evaluation's process line	20
Figure 2 – Traffic Light Grading System	22

Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
EU	European Union
EES	External Evaluation Strategy
WP	Work Package
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PM	Predictive Maintenance
KA2	Key Action 2
OBJ	Objective
VET	Vocational Education and Training
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
CCIs	Cultural and Creative Industries
EACEA	European Education and Culture Executive Agency
EQAB	External Quality Assurance Board
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
PMP	Project management plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
M	Month
N/A	Not Available
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development

Terminology	
Evaluation	Systematic collection and analysis of information on the actual performance of a project. Its aim is to analyze the relevance, progress, success, and cost-effectiveness of the project. An evaluation compares planned results with the actual results of a project. It is a diagnostic tool.
Monitoring	Continuing management exercise. When implementing a project, monitoring deals exclusively with the conversion of inputs into outputs. This exercise will help evaluate if what was supposed to be done really is. Adjustments to the project are possible when monitoring is done throughout the project management life cycle.
Performance indicators	Indicators that provide information (either quantitative or qualitative) on the extent to which the results of a project have been achieved. Evaluation is often confused with indicators used to evaluate. Any activity which aims at interpreting results, or data

	obtained from indicators, are part of an evaluation. To assure that the evaluation process leads to good decision-making, it must rest on correct and precise indicators.
DAC criteria	OECD DAC Network on Development Evaluation (EvalNet) has defined six evaluation criteria – relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability – and two principles for their use. These criteria provide a normative framework used to determine the merit or worth of an intervention (policy, strategy, program, project or activity). They serve as the basis upon which evaluative judgements are made.
Relevance	Refers to the extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries, global, country, and partner/institution needs, policies, and priorities , and continue to do so if circumstances change.
Coherence	Refers to the extent to which the intervention is logically connected and mutually reinforcing with existing policies or other projects. It assesses how well the various components of an initiative work together towards achieving the intended goals and objectives.
Efficiency	Refers to producing planned outputs within budgetary limits and established deadlines. For example: Was the implementation of the project professionally managed?
Effectiveness	Refers to achieving planned results and contributing to attain established goals and objectives. For example: To what extent were the project’s objectives achieved?
Sustainability	Refers to the ability to maintain or support an intervention continuously over time .
Impact	A general statement of desired outcomes to be achieved over a specified period (the reasons for which the National Agency wishes to undertake the project).

Executive Summary

This document introduces the External Evaluation Strategy (EES) for the PreMETS project, a dynamic guide set to evolve with input from project partners. The EES aims to delineate a robust evaluation methodology and a critical framework, essential for guiding consortium partners towards achieving high-quality and relevant deliverables, outcomes, and results. These are meant to align with both the project's specific objectives and the overarching goals of the program. The strategy, to be utilized by an external evaluator, encompasses the creation of interim and final External Evaluation reports, extending up to month 36 of the project.

The report comprises the following sections:

1. Introduction (Section 1): This section presents the project's Objectives and Goals, which stem from the broader objectives of the program. It also emphasizes the scope, significance, and reach of the EES.

2. Monitoring and Evaluation Approaches (Section 2): The report reviews established monitoring and evaluation methodologies from existing literature. These approaches are critical for gauging the progress and success of various programs and projects.

3. Detailed Evaluation Strategy (Section 3): This section deep dives into the chosen monitoring and evaluation strategy, focusing on how it aligns with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and specific objectives of the Erasmus+ Program. It outlines the evaluation criteria, indicators, and analytical tools to be employed in the evaluation process. Additionally, an Impact Weight Assessment for each Work Package (WP) is conducted, highlighting key results and outcomes, their priority levels, and potential risks.

The concluding section offers a succinct summary of the key outcomes of the evaluation strategy. It also provides insights for future evaluations, emphasizing the importance of continuous improvement in project effectiveness.

1. Introduction

The “PreMETS” project is an Erasmus+ Alliances for Education and Enterprises project aiming at introducing an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance (PM) through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training for the development of a coherent digital platform that covers all aspects of the PM training process.

Alliances for Education and Enterprises are transnational, structured and result-driven projects under KA2 of the Erasmus+ Program, in which partners share common goals and work together to foster innovation, new skills, a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial mind-sets. They bring together enterprises and both higher education and vocational training providers to work together in partnership. Operating within one economic sector or several different economic sectors, they create reliable and sustainable relations and demonstrate their innovative and transnational character in all aspects.

They intend to achieve one or more of the following aims:

- Fostering new, innovative, and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning: fostering innovation in education design and delivery, teaching methods, assessment techniques, learning environments and/or developing new skills;
- Supporting skills development in the deep tech domains; supporting Europe’s innovation capacity by broadening its talent pool in these new, disruptive technologies;
- Fostering the setting up of incubators within education and training institutions across Europe;
- Fostering corporate social responsibility (e.g. equity, inclusion, climate change, environmental protection, and sustainable development);
- Stimulating a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial attitudes, mind-sets and skills in learners, educational staff, and other workers, in line with the Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp);
- Improving the quality and relevance of skills developed and certified through education and training systems (including new skills and tackling skills mismatches);
- Facilitating the flow and co-creation of knowledge between higher education and vocational education and training, research, the public sector, and the business sector;

- Building and supporting effective and efficient higher education and vocational education and training systems, which are connected and inclusive, and contribute to innovation.

The general objectives of PreMETS, linked to the above goals of the call “Partnerships for Innovation: Lot1-Alliances for Education and Enterprises”, are:

- OBJ1: Develop an innovative cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral PM education toolkit (ECTS and ECVET compliant) that will be used to train 1000+ PM learners (students, VET learners) and workforce during the project implementation.
- OBJ2: Develop a cutting-edge toolkit for trainers in the field of PM (higher education, vocational education, corporate) that would be uptaken by 250+ trainers during the project implementation.
- OBJ3: Develop a micro-credential certification framework for PM-related micro-courses that would enable at least 500 learners (students, VET learners, workforce) to receive certification for skill-recognition,
- OBJ4: Develop a cross-disciplinary platform that would include the PM education toolkit, the package for PM trainers, the micro-credential certification system, an embedded lifecycle analysis process calculation service (that can be used by learners to test various resilient PM strategies and assess their environmental, social, and economic impacts) and a virtual space for blended Teaching Factories deployment.
- OBJ5: Pilot the training courses and the platform via innovative work-based learning blended apprenticeship secondments where mixed learners from academia, VET, and industry (under the moderation of trainers and experts) will experiment the gained know-how in cyber-physical industrial settings.

The present document presents the **EES of the PreMETS project**. The report focuses on explaining the methodology and the critical framework for assessing quality and relevance of project deliverables, expected outcomes and results, and enhancing the project's effectiveness, impact, and overall success. In this context, the evaluation criteria, and analytical tools for the evaluation process as well as a comprehensive list of important results and outcomes from every work package and their impact weight to the project will be presented.

The EES is elaborated under the WP6: Monitoring and Evaluation, which ensures the effective and qualitative project content and activity development and has as sub-objectives the following:

- To safeguard the compliance and format of the project's activities and outputs;
- To certify traceability of the project's actions and outcomes;
- To recognize and categorize potential problems or weaknesses in the project's actions and results with the purpose of remedy them;
- To review the projects results vis-à-vis expected impact;
- To assess the project's results per identified target-group.

The methodology adopted to create PreMETS's EES is described in detail in section 3.

2. Monitoring and Evaluation Approaches

Evaluation approaches and evaluation methods are both used to assess the effectiveness and impact of programs, policies, or interventions. However, they refer to different aspects of the evaluation process. Evaluation approaches refer to the overall framework or perspective that guides the evaluation. They define the philosophical, theoretical, and methodological principles that underpin the evaluation. Evaluation methods, on the other hand, are the specific techniques and tools used to collect and analyze data to evaluate the program or project. Methods can be quantitative (e.g., surveys, experiments, statistical analysis) or qualitative (e.g., interviews, focus groups, content analysis), and may vary depending on the evaluation approach used. An evaluation method is narrower than an evaluation approach, comprises a procedure outlining how to deal with empirical data, be it qualitative or quantitative: e.g., how to conduct different types of interviews, how to create and analyze datasets, how to conduct desk reviews of specific documents etc.

For monitoring and evaluation, there are several approaches that have been developed to address specific evaluation questions or challenges and they refer to an integrated package of methods and processes. Monitoring and evaluation approaches are essential for any organization for measuring the progress and success of any project or program. Every approach includes principles, methods and tools that can be used for projects that have the ambition to contribute to innovation, but they differ widely in their vision on reality, the on-going processes, and their results and how to support, manage or adjust these processes. Deciding which method is the best depends heavily on the nature of the project, its context, and the monitoring and evaluation objectives. In general, the following approaches can be identified:

- Results-oriented approach,
- Participatory approach,
- Theory-based evaluation approach,
- Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) for learning approach,
- Case study evaluation approach,
- Impact Evaluation approach.

2.1 Results-oriented approach

The emphasis on result-oriented monitoring and evaluation lies in “measuring”: to what degree have the original project objectives and subsequent interventions been achieved? Thus, it emphasizes the importance of measuring outcomes and impact rather than just activities. This approach involves setting specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) indicators for a project and tracking progress against these indicators. This approach is based on assumptions and expectations of causality and linearity: ‘If we do this in the project, then this will happen and this or that change will take place; to put it another way, the project can plan for change and then measure it.’ The strength of result-oriented approaches lies in strategy and planning. They force project managers and participants to consider carefully what they want their contribution to be and how they think they should act to achieve this. In other words, they support the development or explication of the intervention strategy (Van Mierlo, 2011).

Result-oriented approaches are powerful instruments, but they have their limitations in (system) innovation processes. Collective learning and innovation processes do not evolve in a linear way but are unpredictable. As a consequence, cause and effect relations are not easily traceable. So, these approaches do not address the value of collective learning and the development of a shared understanding of the project and/or its context (Van Mierlo, 2011).

2.2 Participatory approach

Participatory monitoring and evaluation approach is a form of qualitative evaluation used to measure the progress and outcomes of a project or program. This approach actively involves key stakeholders, especially the intended beneficiaries of a project or programme, in the design and implementation of the evaluation. Participatory evaluation can be carried out for many reasons. The two most common are to empower beneficiaries to better analyze and improve their own situations, and to produce better and more reliable findings and recommendations. A participatory evaluation can be applied as a specific form of evaluation on its own, or it can be applied in combination with other forms of evaluation such as impact evaluation or theory-based evaluation. It is most likely to be applied where: a project or programme is designed to affect the lives of many different beneficiaries; the impact of a project or programme may be realized in many ways; a project or programme is designed to address issues around social inclusion; a project or programme is concerned with mobilization,

empowerment, or other forms of social development and/or the organization carrying out the evaluation is committed to a rights-based approach (Bakewell et. al. 2003, Guijt 2014, ActionAid 2016).

2.3 Theory-based evaluation approach

Theory-based evaluation approach is usually based on an explicit theory of change or logic model that explains the theory of a development intervention or set of interventions. As it is also described in EIT's monitoring, learning and evaluation (MEL) framework, Theories of change (or logic models) generally include a chain of results from inputs, activities, and outputs through to outcomes and impact, thereby showing the links between causes and effects (EIT MEL, 2021). Theories of change may be very simple – such as the kind of logic model contained within a standard logical framework – or much more complicated. A theory-based approach normally attempts to assess change at each stage of the theory to test the linkages (assumptions) between different levels of change. Essentially, a theory-based approach sets out to test the theory to see if it holds true. If it does, the job of the evaluator is to produce a plausible case, with evidence, that shows what has changed, and explains how a development intervention contributed to that change (White, 2009).

Theory-based approaches can only be used when there is some kind of predicted change to assess. They may not be appropriate very early on in a project or programme before the project / programme has had time to contribute to changes at outcome or impact level. Equally, it would not be appropriate when a project or programme is genuinely exploratory – in other words when the potential outcomes / impact is not known and cannot reasonably be estimated beforehand (White, 2009). The following steps elicit the theory of change underlying a planned project/programme (Weiss, 1995). A precondition is that the evaluator works collaboratively with a wide range of stakeholders.

- *Step 1:* The focus is on the long-term vision of a programme and is likely to relate to a timescale that lies beyond its timeframe. Its aim should be closely linked to the existence of a dimensional, multi-dimensional or group of problems.
- *Step 2:* Having agreed the ultimate aim of the programme, stakeholders are encouraged to consider the necessary outcomes that will be required by the end of the programme if such an aim is to be met in the longer term. Within a

programme they might, for instance, anticipate a decrease in gap between the most and least deprived areas.

- *Steps 3 and 4:* Stakeholders are asked to articulate the types of outputs and short-term outcomes that will help them achieve the specified targets. These might include implementing technological innovations and breakthroughs in the domain of predictive maintenance through learning material. At this stage those involved with the programme consider the most appropriate activities or interventions required to bring about the required change. Different strategies of engagement might be used to target different learner groups depending on their educational level, work experience, etc.
- *Step 5:* Finally, stakeholders consider the resources that can realistically be brought to bear on the planned interventions. These will include staff and organisational capacity, the existence of supportive networks and facilities as well as financial capability.

Following a collective and iterative process the resulting project/programme theory must fulfill certain criteria: it must be plausible, doable and testable. It needs to be articulated in such a way that it can be open to evaluation; this is only possible where there is a high degree of specificity concerning the desired outcomes. Only then, the theory of change that is elicited should be interrogated to ensure that the underlying logic is one that is acceptable to stakeholders either because of the existing evidence base or because it seems likely to be true in a normative sense. The evaluator then takes the programme map generated through this process and, using various data (qualitative and quantitative) collection techniques as relevant, monitors and analyses the unfolding of the programme in practice and integrates the findings.

2.4 Monitoring & Evaluation for learning approach

M&E for learning is an approach that prioritizes learning and program improvement, as opposed to solely focusing on accountability and reporting to external stakeholders. It is an iterative process that involves continuous monitoring, feedback, and reflection to enable learning and adaptation. By engaging stakeholders in the evaluation process, M&E for learning can identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement, and use this information to

guide program design and implementation. Ultimately, the goal of M&E for learning is to create a culture of continuous learning within organizations, where learning and adaptation are integrated into every aspect of program design and implementation.

2.5 Case study evaluation approach

Case-based approach focuses on the systematic generation and analysis of cases (sometimes known as case studies or stories of change). Cases may be based around any unit of analysis, such as people, communities, projects, programs, institutions, policies, or events. Most case-based approaches include both the analyses of individual cases, and analysis across multiple cases. They can be used in any type of work (e.g., service delivery, capacity development, policy influencing) and in any sector of work (e.g., health, education, governance). They are a valuable tool for assessing the program's effectiveness over time, as it enables researchers to compare the results of different interventions and track changes in program outcomes. However, they are not always the best approach if the need is to generate universal findings – that is findings that may be applicable in many different situations. For example, a set of cases designed to examine how community-based organizations influence local government practices in a specific locality may generate conclusions that could apply elsewhere within that locality, but the conclusions may not be relevant for other localities. This is because case studies tend to focus on change and contribution to change within a specific context. Outside of that context, any findings may not be valid (Stern et. al. 2012).

2.6 Impact Evaluation approach

Impact evaluation approaches aim to assess whether the predicted changes brought about through a project or programme have happened or not. The meaning of impact evaluation differs depending on how impact is defined. For example, some define impact narrowly, only including long-term changes in the lives of targeted beneficiaries. Others use wider definitions that also include changes in areas such as policies or capacities. However, there is generally broad agreement that an impact evaluation involves a few features that distinguishes it from other kinds of evaluation. Although other kinds of evaluation may cover one or more of the features in the list below, an impact evaluation would normally be expected to cover all of them:

- Impact evaluations seek to assess the changes brought about by a project or programme, rather than focusing on activities and outputs only;

- They aim to assess predicted change, although many cover unexpected or negative change as well;
- They attempt to assess the contribution of a development intervention (or set of interventions) to any identified change; and
- They usually follow a rigorous and accepted research methodology to identify change and contribution.

Impact evaluations can be carried out on any kind of work, including service delivery, capacity development, mobilization and policy influencing, and any sector of work from health through to governance. An impact evaluation can be applied at any level of work from small projects through to complex programmes covering multiple organizations, sectors, and geographic locations.

An impact evaluation can be carried out for the same reasons as any other kind of evaluation – e.g., to improve projects and programmes, demonstrate accountability, and contribute to wider learning. However, impact evaluations have the potential to provide more certainty about any findings, because they are more rigorous in their approach. On the other hand, they also tend to be more costly than other kinds of evaluation and may take longer to plan and implement. Therefore, the costs and benefits of carrying out an impact evaluation always need to be carefully weighed up (Stern 2015, Perrin 2012, Rogers 2012, ActionAid 2016).

A comparative analysis of the above approaches, in terms of their benefits and challenges, is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Monitoring and evaluation approaches

M & E APPROACH	BENEFITS	CHALLENGES
RESULTS-ORIENTED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tracks project success more accurately, allowing to identify any issues or successes early in the process. ▪ Tracks changes in the conditions and circumstances. ▪ Focuses on the areas of greatest need and priority. ▪ Maximizes project’s impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data collection and analysis: how data are gathered and stored, who is responsible for providing the information, who is analyzing the data. ▪ Information presentation: who has access to the evaluated information, how it should be reported on and disseminated, and what format it should take. ▪ Protocols: clear set of protocols in place to ensure that the data gathered is presented in an accessible and relevant way, with appropriate reporting measures.

M & E APPROACH	BENEFITS	CHALLENGES
PARTICIPATORY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provides a more comprehensive assessment of project by allowing community members to provide feedback on their experiences. ▪ Provides a greater understanding of the local context and an effective way to assess the impact of the project. ▪ Emphasizes on the importance of both quantitative and qualitative data. ▪ Ensures that the voices of community members are heard throughout the evaluation process. ▪ Encourages active collaboration between all stakeholders, leading to more successful development outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limitations (time, resources etc.) ▪ Stakeholders representation in the process should be accurate and adequate. ▪ Methods of data collection and analysis should be reliable. ▪ Evaluation results should be used to inform future actions. ▪ Stakeholders should understand how to interpret and use evaluation results correctly in order to maximize their usefulness.
THEORY-BASED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identifies potential gaps, solutions and areas for improvement and expansion. ▪ Provides a comprehensive way to assess the overall effectiveness of the project. ▪ Allows for an examination of the assumptions on which the project is based and provides insight into how it can be improved or expanded for better results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Understanding of the underlying theoretical assumptions that shape the research methods, sampling strategies, and analysis techniques should be clear. ▪ Indicators and measures should be clear so as to ensure that each individual theory is explored and assessed thoroughly.
MONITORING AND EVALUATION (M&E) FOR LEARNING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prioritizes internal learning and program improvement. ▪ Involves a collaborative process of data collection, analysis, and interpretation, with a focus on identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. ▪ Engages a wide range of stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Defining clear learning outcomes. ▪ Developing appropriate indicators. ▪ Data collection and analysis. ▪ Attribution and causality. ▪ Stakeholder engagement. ▪ Sustainability.
CASE STUDY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provides in-depth insight into a particular project. ▪ Provides a reality check on how successful programs are actually working, allowing organizations to make adjustments as needed. ▪ Identify any underlying issues that need to be addressed. ▪ Uncover experiential information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need to establish a contextually relevant research design that accounts for the unique factors of the case being studied. ▪ Availability of resources and personnel, allocated to data collection and analysis. ▪ Confidentiality issues.
IMPACT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Focuses on understanding the impact of a specific project or intervention on a population. ▪ Looks at both short-term and long-term impacts, as well as unintended consequences. ▪ Provides a more comprehensive understanding of how the intervention affected its target audience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Difficulty on capturing immediate outcomes, as the effects may take a long time to become clear. ▪ Complexity ▪ Time limitations ▪ Involvement of different elements and actors – difficulty in isolating cause-and-effect relationships and pinpoint

M & E APPROACH	BENEFITS	CHALLENGES
		exactly what has caused a certain outcome

In the next section (Section 3), the report details the chosen evaluation approach for the external evaluation reports. This section will provide a comprehensive analysis, weighing the advantages and disadvantages of each evaluation method under consideration.

3. Evaluation Strategy

3.1 Evaluation Approach

The EES is an important component of PreMETS project legacy that complies with the program's evaluation roadmap and as a result with the requirements of the Better Regulation Guidelines¹ and the Erasmus+ legal base².

The External Evaluation Strategy (EES) is designed to methodically evaluate the performance of the PreMETS project. This process involves comparing the project's outcomes with initial expectations as outlined in the impact assessment (D.7.9) and the stipulations of any relevant legislation. The EES seeks to identify not only the expected results but also any unintended or unforeseen effects that were not previously anticipated or addressed in the impact assessment or the legislative framework.

Furthermore, the EES aims to draw definitive conclusions about the ongoing suitability of the intervention. It assesses whether the project continues to meet its intended purpose or if adjustments are necessary to enhance its effectiveness, relevance, and coherence. This assessment also considers the need to reduce any undue burdens or inconsistencies. In cases where the project no longer aligns with its intended goals, the EES may recommend its repeal.

A result-oriented evaluation approach that focuses on monitoring and self-assessment of project progress towards specific outcomes and results will be followed. The external evaluation will be made from a group of 5 independent experts in the field of Predictive Manufacturing (PM), which formulate the External Quality Assurance Board (EQAB). The EQAB will use the external evaluation strategy described in this document to repeatedly assess whether the project milestones, objectives are reached. This will be done with annual EQAB meetings with the PreMETS General Project Coordinator (CERTH) and the Quality Assurance Manager (HELIX). The timeline and set of evaluation material are defined during the project implementation by the PreMETS Strategic Committee (SC).

This approach is goal-driven and requires a clear understanding of the desired results. It involves setting clear and measurable criteria and performance indicators, developing an action plan, and continuously tracking progress toward the project and program goals more

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/smart-regulation/guidelines/toc_guide_en.htm

² Regulation No 1288/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing 'Erasmus+': the Union programme for education, training, youth and sport (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 50).

accurately, related to the other approaches, allowing to identify any issues or successes early in the process. It is important to monitor systematically the progress and the effects of the implementation because in case of absence of such information, it will be difficult to evaluate the intervention appropriately and to rectify problems or improve delivery of the desired result.

In the selection of the approach, the overall program evaluation approach was also taken into account. Programme evaluation is following the same pattern, adopting a result-oriented approach aiming at assessing the effectiveness of the Erasmus+ actions in achieving the programme's objectives and the efficiency of the Programme and its European added value as well as the long-term results and impact of the predecessor programs. It also addresses the Programme's internal and external coherence, the continued relevance of its objectives, and the scope for simplification. Typically, results-oriented monitoring and evaluation follows a life-cycle approach — that is, an approach aligned with the key stages of the project and program cycle.

In this context, the Programme monitoring is done through a combination of tools:

- Analysis of Programme performance indicators;
- Analysis of the internal project reports (to check the progress, take remedial action, update action plans, and allow on-going data collection and preparation of progress reports);
- Monitoring missions (usually annual missions to review the performance of approved projects and the Programme for further improvements);
- Mid Term Evaluation of the Erasmus+ Programme;
- Final evaluation of the Erasmus+ Programme.

At the same time, and to be aligned with the Program's evaluation plan, the external evaluation methodology of the project/interventions is based on an explicit set of **relevant tools** that considers the following elements:

- Indicators, target values and sources of verification;
- Baselines for the indicators set by the project;
- Type of evaluations needed, their timing and results;
- Frequency and content of project progress reports (project coordinator and beneficiaries);

- Project timetable of implementation and reporting requirements.

A process line, depicting in simple steps the evaluation methodology that will be adopted, is reflected on **Figure 1** below:

Figure 1 – The evaluation's process line

Evaluation findings are based on a wide range of data sources systematically triangulated i.e., cross-checked against each other: programme documentation, programme data and views of the managing bodies, views of direct beneficiaries as well as nonbeneficiaries, EU and national stakeholders, policy makers, programme countries, bodies in charge of implementation of other comparable programmes and the general public.

Data collection and review - Inputs for the interim and final evaluation reports

Progress/ Interim Reports

Interim/ progress reports present the interim, preliminary, or initial evaluation findings. They focus on events and tactical details like progress drivers and anticipated roadblocks. The goal of a progress report is to assess where the project has been and what are the next steps. The beneficiaries issue periodical progress/interim reports on a defined basis based on the provisions of the contract. The quality of the reports is supplemented by the relevant information, activities, and resource schedule of the reporting periods.

Outputs/ Activities/ Deliverables

Another important source of information are the internal documents, including reports, deliverables, and outputs. The final evaluation report reviews the actual progress of activities, in content and timing, and use of resources against what is planned and examine whether that also corresponds to what is reasonably needed. The consolidation of data produced during each reporting period, analysing the whole set of progress reports available at the expert's disposal to obtain the necessary knowledge and understanding of the state of play, ensure a sound analysis and draw of useful conclusions.

Interviews

Interviewing is used as a methodology for both quantitative and qualitative evaluation. The interviews are designed and organised on an “unstructured” set-up, notably informal and conversational discussion with representatives from the coordinating beneficiary in the basis of a qualitative approach, including only topic areas and themes rather than standard questions. During the interviews, data and narrative information are collected, in order to better understand the respondent’s subjective perspectives. A standard indicative form interviews is proposed hereby:

- Short description of the participant profile.
- What is your general feedback from the project experience?
- Pros and cons according to your experience
- Has the project changed your way of thinking of work organization?
- Has the project changed your way of working actually?
- What are your general conclusions and recommendations?

The interviews with the involved stakeholders can be conducted through various ways: questionnaires sent via email or chatting apps, telephone calls, online interviews, face-to-face discussions etc.

Analysis and qualitative scoring

Analysis

The analysis of the data and information collected is performed on the basis of data comparison between what has been delivered and what was contractually expected to be delivered on the foreseen timeframe and budget.

Scoring

Qualitative scoring based on a traffic light grading system is used (see **figure 2**). This provides a quick overview of the status of the interventions at the level of each monitoring question. A three-grade scale is adopted using the following categories:

The grade is coherent with the finding; the justification of the grade emerges clearly from the analysis.

Green - good or very good	The situation is considered satisfactory, but there may be room for improvement. Recommendations are useful, but not vital to the intervention.
	There are issues to be addressed, otherwise the global performance of may be negatively affected. Necessary improvements do not however require a major revision of the logic and implementation arrangements.
Red – off track or with serious deficiencies	There are deficiencies which are so serious that, if not addressed, they may lead to failure of the intervention. Major adjustments and revision of the intervention logic and/or implementation arrangements are necessary.

Figure 2 – Traffic Light Grading System

The evaluation reports that will be elaborated throughout the project duration put specific focus on commenting on crosscutting issues (mainstreaming themes) and on the possible identification of lessons learned and good practices.

Conclusions and recommendations

The conclusions and recommendations of the interim and final evaluation reports will be drawn applying the key principles of the results-oriented monitoring methodology according to the following six DAC criteria of **relevance, coherence, efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability**, that will be further analysed on Section 3.2.

3.2 Evaluation Criteria

The evaluation criteria's purpose is to support consistent, high-quality evaluation within a common framework. They provide a normative framework with which to assess a specific intervention. The criteria can also be used in processes beyond evaluation, including defining frameworks and indicators for monitoring and results management, funding approval, strategic planning, and intervention design, particularly to improve future interventions. Collectively, there is value in having commonly defined criteria that are similarly applied across interventions. The criteria also provide a consistent language across the development field, providing standardisation and allowing for comparison and learning across interventions. The evaluation criteria are not a methodology, and they are not the goals that an intervention is trying to achieve. Instead, they provide prompts for asking the right questions during the evaluation of an intervention.

Because every intervention (the entity being evaluated) is different, the evaluation process needs to be flexible, and the use of evaluation criteria should be thoughtful and adapted to the purpose and users. External evaluator should think critically about which criteria are most useful to support high-quality, useful evaluation that will be valuable to the intended users. The following six aspects and their related questions will assist in the thoughtful application of the criteria:

- **Context:** What is the context of the intervention itself and how can the criteria be understood in the context of the individual evaluation, the intervention, and the stakeholders?
- **Purpose:** What is the evaluation trying to achieve and what questions are most useful in pursuing and fulfilling this purpose?
- **Roles and power dynamics:** Who are the stakeholders, what are their respective needs and interests? What are the power dynamics between them? Who needs to be involved in deciding which criteria to apply and how to understand them in the local context? This could include questions about ownership and who decides what is evaluated and prioritized.
- **Intervention (evaluand):** What type of intervention is being evaluated (a project, policy, strategy, sector)? What is its scope and nature? How direct or indirect are its expected results? What complex systems thinking are at play?

- **Evaluability:** Are there any constraints in terms of access, resources, and data (including disaggregated data) impacting the evaluation, and how does this affect the criteria?
- **Timing:** At which stage of the intervention's lifecycle will the evaluation be conducted? Has the context in which the intervention is operating changed over time and if so, how? Should these changes be considered during the evaluation? The timing will influence the use of the criteria as well as the source of evidence.

The most important aspect of deciding how to use the criteria is **relating them to the aim of the evaluation and its context and then building the evaluation criteria and questions around this purpose.**

The criteria are not intended to be applied in a standard, fixed way for every intervention or used in a tick-box fashion. Indeed, the criteria should be carefully interpreted or understood in relation to the intervention being evaluated. This encourages flexibility and adaptation of the criteria to each individual evaluation. It should be clarified which specific concepts in the criteria will be drawn upon in the evaluation and why.

The purpose of the evaluation should be carefully and clearly defined. Stakeholders involved in the evaluation should be included at this stage to ensure that they understand the goal of the evaluation and how it will be used.

Key questions to look at when determining the purpose of the evaluation include:

- What is the demand for an evaluation, who is the target audience and how will they use the findings?
- What is feasible given the characteristics and context of the intervention?
- What degree of certainty is needed when answering the key questions?
- When is the information needed?
- What is already known about the intervention and its results? Who has this knowledge and how are they using it?

Quality and ethical standards should inform subsequent thinking about methodological approaches, design, implementation, and management of the evaluation process.

When adjusting the criteria to a specific evaluation, it is also important to delve into causality and gauge the extent to which the evaluation will be able to attribute effects to the intervention being assessed. These considerations can help manage stakeholder expectations and determine which criteria will be covered in depth. This is most crucial for effectiveness and impact, but it is also indirectly applicable to, and may feed into, other criteria. For example, efficiency and sustainability could use the actual (or projected) benefits attributed to the intervention as assessed under effectiveness and impact.

The key points that are considered, where relevant, as regards the selection of the DAS evaluation criteria and their adaptation to the external evaluation purpose of PreMETS project, are provided below. It should be noted that coherence is jointly evaluated together with the relevance.

Relevance and coherence

- Design process of the project proposal/methods to involve local stakeholders (local ownership).
- Successful synergies and networking with stakeholders inside and outside the project.
- Coordination, complementarity, and EU added value.
- Complementarities and synergies established with other interventions.
- Intervention logic, Monitoring, and learning
- Log frame and indicators.
- Knowledge/Learning system put in place.
- Reporting and monitoring systems put in place.

Efficiency

- Internal management and communication, including internal knowledge management practices.
- Funding modalities (when conducive to ensuring relevance, efficiency, effectiveness and/or sustainability of the project).
- Implementation modalities found particularly innovative, efficient and/or cost-effective.

Effectiveness

- Effectiveness of activities such as: dialogue models/ methods used to increase civil society participation/ to increase dialogue between state authorities and CCIs/ also between CCIs and other businesses of the private sector.
- Effectiveness of activities such as: Capacity development, i.e., training and mentoring methods, processes, follow-up.
- Effectiveness of activities such as: Advocacy, i.e., strategies used to promote legislative changes, etc.
- Effectiveness of activities such as: External communicational policies and practices.

Sustainability

- Actions to support the sustainability of local stakeholder activities.
- EU practices, i.e., coordination between other networks.
- Existence of exit/ handover strategies.

Another criterion that is horizontally applied/considered throughout the evaluation of all criteria is the **impact** which corresponds to the broader change in the political, social, economic and/or environmental global context which tends to be long-term and stems from the combined effort of the project activities. It is a detectable improvement in the lives of people based on economic, social, cultural, institutional, environmental, technological changes.

In brief, the DAC criteria used for drafting the conclusion and recommendations of the evaluation reports are broken down as follows:

Relevance #1. Are we doing the right things?

Relevance looks at the relationship between the needs and problems in society and the objectives of the intervention. Things change over time, certain objectives may be met or superseded; needs and problems change, new ones arise. The extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries' global, country, and partner – institution needs, policies and priorities, and continue to do so if circumstances change.

- Do the interventions constitute an adequate response to the current needs and rights of the target groups / end beneficiaries?

- Are the interventions adapted to the present institutional, human, and financial capacities of the partner government and/ or other key stakeholder(s) with a role in implementation?
- Do the interventions show a high degree of alignment with key EU priorities?
- Is the choice of IP/method of implementation proving to be appropriate?
- Do all key stakeholders demonstrate effective commitment to the objectives of the interventions (i.e., ownership)?

Coherence #2. How well does the intervention fit?

Coherence is connected with relevance. While relevance assesses the intervention at the level of the needs and priorities of the stakeholders and beneficiaries that are directly involved, coherence goes up to the next level and looks at the fit of the intervention within the broader system. Both relevance and coherence consider how the intervention aligns with the context, but they do so from different perspectives.

Effectiveness #3. Is it working?

The extent to which the intervention achieved, its intended objectives, and its results, including any differential results across groups.

- Are the outputs being achieved with the expected quality?
- To what extent are results inclusive i.e. ensuring the fair distribution of effects across different groups of the population?
- Does the intervention effectively influence the partner's relevant policy and interventions?
- Is the intervention having any unintended positive or negative effects? Were the negative effects considered for possible (risk) mitigation?

Efficiency #4. Are we doing things well?

Efficiency considers the cost-effective and timely relationship between the resources used by an intervention and the changes it generates (which may be positive or negatives). Resources include staff, purchases, time and money spent on fixed costs, running costs and administrative burden. The extent to which the intervention delivers, or is likely to deliver results, in an economic and timely way.

- Are the implementation mechanisms proving to be appropriate to achieve planned outputs and contribute to outcomes?
- Are the inputs/ resources provided by the various stakeholders (still) adequate for achieving the planned results?
- Has the intervention encountered any delays and was the planning revised accordingly?
- Is spending in line with the budget?

Sustainability #5. – Will the benefits last?

Sustainability relates to the continuation of benefits from an intervention after major support has been completed. The probability of continued long-term benefits. The resilience to risk of the net benefit flows over time. It has various dimensions: social, economic, political, environmental, financial, institutional, etc.

- Are key stakeholders attaining the necessary capacities (incl. institutional, human, and financial) to ensure the continued flow of benefits/ services?
- Is access to the benefits generated by the intervention affordable for target groups over the long term?
- Has the private sector been sufficiently involved with a view to contributing to the sustainability of the interventions?
- Does the intervention increase resilience to shocks and pressure (by addressing specific dimensions of fragility and their root causes)?

Impact #6. – What difference does the intervention make?

Impact addresses the ultimate significance and potentially transformative effects of the intervention. It seeks to identify social, environmental, and economic effects of the intervention that are longer term or broader in scope than those already captured under the effectiveness criterion. Beyond the immediate results, this criterion seeks to capture the indirect, secondary, and potential consequences of the intervention. It does so by examining the holistic and enduring changes in systems or norms, and potential effects on people's well-being, human rights, gender equality, and the environment.

- Has the intervention caused a significant change in the lives of the intended beneficiaries?

- How did the intervention cause higher-level effects (such as changes in norms or systems)?
- Did all the intended target groups, including the most disadvantaged and vulnerable, benefit equally from the intervention?
- Is the intervention transformative – does it create enduring changes in norms – including gender norms – and systems, whether intended or not?
- Is the intervention leading to other changes, including “scalable” or “replicable” results?
- How will the intervention contribute to changing society for the better?

Evaluating relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, sustainability, and impact is often challenging. Impact is the one that can often be the most challenging to evaluate and understand. In **Table 2** the main challenges involved, together with some suggestions on how the external evaluator should proceed, are summarised.

Table 2: Challenges of evaluation criteria (Source: OECD)

CRITERIA	CHALLENGES	HOW TO ADDRESS: EVALUATOR
Relevance	There are many national and international stakeholders to consider who have multiple and potentially competing priorities and needs.	A strong analysis of relevance should consider potential and actual trade-offs in responses to needs. The relevance of beneficiaries should be the most important consideration when looking at needs and priorities. Ownership and participation are also helpful for managing this challenge and in ensuring that competing priorities are accounted for and, where possible, balanced.
	Understanding if an intervention has clear and appropriate objectives and how they were determined.	To make a strong assessment of relevance, an intervention’s objectives are a critical starting point. This can be a challenge if they are not clearly articulated. Evaluators should critically review the extent to which objectives are sufficiently challenging, reflect the needs of both the intended beneficiaries and the capacities of stakeholders, and explore how these objectives were identified and verified. The suitability of objectives might be further explored under impact to understand whether the objectives contributed to important, transformational changes. In this instance, evaluators should engage closely with programme stakeholders to understand the programme’s objectives, how they were defined and ascertain whether a contingency plan is/was in place. They should assess whether and to what extent these are based on a sound analysis of needs and context. This will form an important starting point for understanding relevance.
	The intervention lacks a clearly articulated theory of change, logic model and/or other explicit design rationale.	Assessment of relevance is aided by a theory of change, logic model and/or other explicit design rationale as this provides important insights for assessing relevance of design. Evaluators should identify if this exists and,

CRITERIA	CHALLENGES	HOW TO ADDRESS: EVALUATOR
	<p>The context changed over time, but it is unclear if – and how – the intervention was adapted.</p>	<p>where necessary, work with stakeholders to help them reconstruct or clearly articulate the theory of change as a starting point for the evaluation.</p> <p>Unfortunately, adaptations are not always well documented. It is necessary to first describe what changes occurred, and how the intervention was (or was not) adapted, in order to then evaluate relevance. If it is clear that the context has changed significantly in ways that might have affected relevance, the evaluators should consult intervention documents (such as annual or quarterly reports, monitoring data, and, if possible, communications such as meeting minutes, announcements to staff and participants) to “reconstruct” the changes that were made and identify key decision points and what drove those decisions.</p>
<p>Coherence</p>	<p>Different contexts/countries - large volume of policy documents, data, and informants to be assessed.</p>	<p>Challenges can only be solved by applying qualitative assessments based on the available sources of data/information. It is also important to assess evaluability during the inception of an evaluation and be open and transparent about limitations. It should be flagged when data sources cannot be accessed. Understand the legislative environment and organizational policies and use knowledge to design appropriate primary data collection and analysis plans.</p>
	<p>Assessing coherence across all relevant policy areas can lead to a very broad scope.</p>	<p>Collaborate with the evaluation manager to ensure priorities and scope are clearly defined at the start of the evaluation.</p>
	<p>The mandates of some evaluation departments may focus only on humanitarian and development assistance, limiting their scope to assess coherence questions across government.</p>	<p>Special attention should be paid at the evaluation design stage to define and refine the scope of the evaluation, and to operationalise how coherence would be explored in line with evaluation departments’ mandates – or to outline limitations in doing so.</p>
	<p>Organisations restricting access to data due to data protection legislation and/or organisational policies.</p>	<p>Ongoing discussions should be held with the evaluation team to support access to data and to develop suitable risk mitigation strategies.</p>
<p>Effectiveness</p>	<p>Lack of appropriate, informative, or disaggregated data.</p>	<p>The availability of data (e.g. a lack of baseline or mid-term assessments) can inhibit the measurement of the achievement of objectives as causality is then more difficult to attribute and it is harder to determine who is contributing what. Baseline data can be reconstructed but this is generally less precise and reliable than properly assembled baseline data. Other approaches evaluators can take include: 1) triangulation and validation of data that is available; 2) use of alternative methods; and 3) the construction of a contribution story.</p>
	<p>Working with poorly phrased, vague, or difficult-to-measure objectives/purpose statements.</p>	<p>Ensure that intervention objectives are verifiable, realistic, and aligned with current international standards for development interventions in the inception phase of an evaluation. The indicators for measuring the achievement of the objectives should also be validated according to generally accepted criteria such as SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Timely). Ideally, this process</p>

CRITERIA	CHALLENGES	HOW TO ADDRESS: EVALUATOR
		should be undertaken in a participatory manner between the evaluators and evaluation managers.
	Attribution of results	The issue of attributing causality or determining contribution is a challenge in evaluating effectiveness, particularly over the longer term. The construction of a contribution story and devising appropriate triangulation of data streams can support the evaluator to identify whether results can be attributed to the intervention being evaluated.
	Finding suitable comparisons	Evaluators usually struggle to find perfect matches, so they use what is available. Yet, they must be cautious in making comparisons and should undertake a sensitivity analysis. For example, efficiency in fragile and conflict-affected situations should only be compared with similarly challenging environments.
Efficiency	Navigating different concepts of efficiency and the associated methods and tools	The literature on the economic concepts of efficiency is extensive and can be consulted by evaluators to decide on which methods and tools are most appropriate given the evaluation at hand.
	Lack of adequate expertise on efficiency analysis	Ensure there is an understanding on what is needed to conduct an efficiency analysis and how to incorporate it into the evaluation process (both in terms of approach and expertise).
	Data and measurement	Available data on benefits, results and costs can be hard to obtain. For example, impact evaluations may provide quantified estimates of changes in outcomes due to the intervention while, generally speaking, leaving out estimates of costs, let alone full costs.
	Time considerations	Both in economic appraisal and in evaluation of efficiency, choices between time periods when resources are used and when results are delivered are a crucial aspect. Results and full costs (e.g. environmental costs) may accrue over many years, so the actual efficiency during the course of the programme, or at the time of the evaluation, may not reflect the entire picture.
Sustainability	If the intervention has not achieved its intended results (assessed via effectiveness), positive unintended benefits or made contributions to impact.	In the case that the intervention has had no benefits, the analysis of sustainability becomes redundant. Evaluators should be clear and open about the limitations of evaluating sustainability and consider focusing on other criteria.
	Timing of the evaluation	Evaluations will often take place during the lifespan of the intervention or may occur at a point where sustainability is not yet evident. Therefore, evaluators should consider focusing on the conditions for sustainability if the intervention is still being implemented or has very recently ended. They should provide a robust assessment of prospective sustainability by identifying factors in the operating environment that could favor sustainability. In this sense, gender analysis is a key and will provide useful and relevant information on the consistency of the structural changes achieved and their effect on reducing inequalities.
	Evaluating factors likely to influence sustainability.	Contextual factors that support (or undermine) prospective sustainability can be assessed qualitatively

CRITERIA	CHALLENGES	HOW TO ADDRESS: EVALUATOR
		and quantitatively. These include but are not limited to stakeholder ownership and engagement, absorptive capacity, political will, and national resource availability.
Impact	Clarity on what impact means as a concept for the relevant stakeholders and users of the evaluation.	Agree at the outset which definition is being used, whether the OECD DAC terminology or a different concept, and follow this consistently. Check with stakeholders regularly during discussions if their interpretation of the term has changed.
	Clarity on what impact was intended for this intervention and how it would be achieved.	This depends on the original design of the intervention and availability of a clear results framework, with a theory of change. If this does not exist, a theory-based evaluation of impact (which is highly desirable) would be difficult, so it will need to be reconstructed which includes reference to specific target groups. Some interventions typically have goals that are too broad and inflated beyond the scope of what the intervention can achieve.
	Identifying the degree to which the intervention causes the impact.	Mapping the pathways of contribution or attribution as appropriate from the intervention to results when these may be less traceable/explicit at higher levels. Use of methods such as contribution analysis can be helpful here. Drawing on specific guidance/methodologies on how to measure impact, explore options and make deliberate and realistic choices on methods driven by the purpose of the evaluation, context, questions to be answered, data availability and resources available for the evaluation and their feasibility. A key question is whether the methods will simply assess the size of the impact for that intervention, or also identify why and how it occurred.
	Availability of data including baselines and indicators.	For assessing higher-level effects, data can be particularly challenging, including lack of baselines and indicators. This is partly an evaluability question to be considered at the outset of the evaluation but also informs the choice of suitable methods to draw on different types of qualitative and quantitative data in the best possible way.
	The intervention has significant unexpected or unintended effects.	It is often difficult to capture unintended or unexpected results as they are often left out of monitoring frameworks and data collection. To capture what is most important for beneficiaries and other people affected by the intervention (positively or negatively) evaluators should remain open to looking beyond the formal project documents and expected data. The relative significance of the effects will likely vary across stakeholders.

3.3 Key Performance Indicators

As already mentioned in Section 3.1, external evaluation methodology will take into account earlier expectations, developed in the context of the impact assessment (D.7.9). Impact assessment set the basis to start measuring and monitoring defined indicators that will be reiterated and extended based on the project's evolution and proposed PreMETS solution. Those key performance indicators (KPIs) are a valuable management tool to monitor progress (and allow adjustments if needed) during the implementation of the project activities and to evaluate the degree of success in achieving its objectives.

KPIs should be "S-M-A-R-T" which stands for:

- **Specific:** Indicators should be crystal clear, focusing on who is doing what and how. The data collected should directly relate to the objective without any confusion.
- **Measurable:** If an indicator cannot be measured progress cannot be tracked down. Hence, once the indicator is clear and specific, it becomes measurable in various ways.
- **Achievable:** The indicator should reflect realistic changes that can be linked to the intervention. It should also have achievable performance targets.
- **Relevant:** The indicators should be a valid measure of the outcome and should be backed by research and expertise. It should align with the theories behind the project.
- **Timely:** The indicators need to be timely in terms of data collection, reflecting the resources available. They should also match the timing of the outcome changes and impact.

SMART indicators can help track progress effectively and ensure that everyone understands what's being measured and why (Gouédard, 2021). It must be kept in mind that a logical system, where different indicators contribute to producing an overall understanding of the different dimensions might influence the achievement of desired outcomes. **The definition of the KPIs assists to properly assess how the impact might vary over time in respect to the following given dimensions:**

- **Societal:** Considers the impact that PreMETS has on its learners, as well as other users considered as potential targets of interest.

- **Governance:** Considers whether institutions are able to use PreMETS to partially overcome potential differences in social capital, through their good governance as well as cross-sectorial cooperation and partnerships
- **Environmental:** Considers whether PreMETS does directly or indirectly contribute to enhance a healthy relationship with the earth and its resources and establish more sustainable behaviors in its users.
- **Economic:** Considers whether industries adopting PreMETS change their employability, income, operating costs, productivity, and competitiveness over time.

A prioritized set of indicators and their measurements defined and selected by the beneficiaries, were presented in the first version of the Impact Assessment Plan of the project (D.7.9). **The indicators defined are based on three (3) variables:**

- **Importance for the Project:** The extent to which the indicator aligns with the project's goals and objectives,
- **Feasibility:** The practicality and ease of data collection and measurement for each indicator,
- **Effort Needed:** The resources, time, and effort required to measure the indicator effectively.

The final KPIs, based on the above variables and dimensions, are listed below:

- **% of trustworthiness in e-learning platforms:** Is the users' trust and acceptance of technologies increased by the active usage of PreMETS?
- **% of interest in e-learning platforms:** Is the interest for e-learning platform solutions increased?
- **Number of trained learners in PM:** How many users are trained on PM that before were not?
- **Number of certified learners via microcredentials:** How many users enrolled have successfully completed the modules and are therefore certified via micro credentials?
- **Number of trained trainers in PM:** How many users are trained on PM that will train other learners?
- **Number of train-the-trainers modules:** How many train-the-trainers modules were adopted?
- **Experience satisfaction:**

- What is the overall learner satisfaction with regards to the PreMETS online platform?
- How many key roles in the companies involved in the pilots and adopting PreMETS were satisfied with the platform as an upskilling tool?
- How many key roles in industrial companies outside of the project were satisfied with the platform as an upskilling tool?
- **Number of targets reached through upskilling and learning networks:** How many targets did PreMETS reach indirectly by transferring its outputs to upskilling and learning networks?
- **Number of website visitors:** Are learners actively visiting and engaging with PreMETS modules and activities?
- **Number of companies engaged:** How many companies engaged with PreMETS platform?
- **Number of universities and VET centers adopting PreMETS:** How many Universities and VET centers did uptake PreMETS platform?
- **Fitness of PreMETS as an upskilling tool** by key roles in companies involved in the pilots adopting the platform: How many external industries were satisfied with the adoption of PreMETS?
- **Number of new skills and competencies gained through PreMETS modules:** Which are the skills and new competencies gained by certified participants through PreMETS modules?
- **Number of learners able to define and structure their own learning path:** Are learners that completed the PreMETS modules able to structure future learning paths?

For each of the above KPIs, a **target value**, that need to be met until the end of the project’s implementation, was set. The project has set very ambitious targets aiming at contributing to the Programmes’ overall achievements.

Table 3: List of indicators and target values.

INDICATOR	TARGET VALUE
% of trustworthiness in e-learning platforms	>45%
% of interest in e-learning platforms	>20%
Number of trained learners in PM	1.000
Number of certified learners via microcredentials	500

INDICATOR	TARGET VALUE
Number of trained trainers in PM	250
Number of train-the-trainers modules	8
Experience satisfaction	>85%
Number of targets reached through upskilling and learning networks	500.000
Number of website visitors	5.000
Number of companies engaged	20
Number of universities and VET centers adopting PreMETS	50
Fitness of PreMETS as an upskilling tool	45%

3.4 Work Package Analysis

In this Section, the results and outcomes expected to be achieved in the context of the project as well as a preliminary assessment of the significance and influence of the anticipated outcomes, priority level and potential risks that may prevent the smooth implementation, along with the timeline and budget for each WP, will be presented.

More specifically, in the external evaluation reports, an analysis of the data and information collected will be performed on the basis of data comparison between what has been delivered and what was contractually expected to be delivered according to the foreseen timeframe and budget. The analysis will be done per WP and deliverable that are contractually expected to have been completed/ delivered during the reference period, for the interim evaluation report and until the end of the project, for the final evaluation report.

3.4.1 WP1: Project management and coordination

WP1 ensures the proper implementation and coordination of the project. The specific objectives are to manage the PreMETS Consortium, ensure communication, monitor project advancement, and oversee project risks and mitigation measures, maintain the link with the EACEA, oversee legal, contractual, IPR, ethical and gender matters and ensure a mentoring/coaching mechanism among the beneficiaries towards better facilitating overall project management. In this context two deliverables will be implemented:

- **D1.1 Project management plan (PMP):** a report containing all internal management and coordination procedures,
- **D1.2 Data management plan (DMP):** a document explaining the PreMETS data management strategy.

Both outputs/ deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not

available).

Start Month: 1

End Month: 36

Budget: 256.673,00 €

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, financial and administrative risks.

Priority: Both deliverables are of high priority and need to be implemented at M1. D.1.1 is an important deliverable and the first milestone of the project that need to be developed and approved in the kick-off by all partners and EQAB during the first month of the project.

3.4.2 WP2: Predictive manufacturing training content development

WP2 is linked to OBJ1 (Develop an innovative cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral PM education toolkit) and OBJ2 (Develop a cutting edge toolkit for trainers) of PreMETS and aims to: engage in foresight exercises to develop the future employee profile(s) in the field of predictive manufacturing, develop the predictive manufacturing training toolkit based on the identified needs (WN1-WN6) and the results of the foresight exercise and develop the predictive manufacturing train-the-trainers toolkit (TN1-TN8). In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

- **D2.1 Future PM employee profile:** a report describing the future employee profile in the field of PM.
- **D2.2 PM training toolkit:** a compendium of documents covering content for **6 training modules:** 300 slides with voice/video overlay, 5 storyboards, 1 booklet (300 pages), collection of 20 demonstrative videos, 1 interactive learner-persona based simulator as assessment tool (180 multiple choice questions) and 1 WebQuest per module related to work-based learning practices.
- **D2.3 PM training toolkit VET certification strategy:** a 15-page report consisting of the VET certification guidelines for the content from D2.2. It will contain number of contact hours, institutional integration guidelines, assessment, and work-based learning integrations.
- **D2.4 PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy:** a 15-page report consisting of the higher education certification guidelines for the content from D2.2. It will contain number of contact hours, institutional integration guidelines, assessment, and work-based learning integrations.

- **D2.5 Train-the-trainers toolkit:** a compendium of documents covering content for **8 training modules:** slides with voice/video overlay (160 in total), 1 storyboard, 1 booklet (160 pages in total), collection of 10 demonstrative videos, 1 interactive learner-persona based simulator as assessment tool (160 questions) and 1 WebQuest per module as an applied online education delivery task.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, their contribution to the achievement of the set targets (number of produced training modules and related material), the existence of weaknesses while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

Start Month: 1
End Month: 12

Budget: 249.378,00€

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, Competitive courses.

Priority: D.2.1 is of high priority and need to be implemented at M3. D.2.2-2.5 will be implemented later during the first year of the project. D.2.2, 2.4 and 2.5, namely PM training content certified in VET and HEI and Train-the-trainers toolkit, are important deliverables and the second and third milestones of the project accordingly.

3.4.3 WP3: Micro credential certification framework

WP3 relates to OBJ3 of PreMETS (Develop a micro-credential certification framework for PM-related micro courses) and has as sub-objectives to develop a micro credential certification framework for PreMETS (for both the PM training toolkit and train-the-trainers toolkit), introduce an operational framework for the institutionalization of the micro credential system and develop and standardize the assessment for the micro credentials. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

- **D3.1 PreMETS certification framework:** an integrated report covering the results of Tasks 3.1 and 3.2 regarding the Micro-credential certification framework and Micro-credential assessment development.
- **D3.2 PreMETS digital certificate/credential:** a digital credential issued via Europass Digital Credentials App as well as a standalone XML certificate file.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

Start Month: 10
End Month: 15

Budget: 123.020,00€

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay.

Priority: D.3.1 and D.3.2 are of medium priority and need to be implemented during M10 and M15. PreMETS digital credential launched in Europass Digital is an important deliverable and the fourth milestone of the project.

3.4.4 WP4: PreMETS Predictive Manufacturing Platform

WP4 relates to OBJ4 of PreMETS (Develop a cross-disciplinary platform) and has as sub-objectives to confirm and refined the platform requirement analysis (functional and technical) performed in the preparation phase, develop, test, and integrate the platform modules/services, populate the platform with content and prepare it for the pilots. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

- **D4.1 PreMETS Platform:** The PreMETS platform successfully launched and tested.
- **D4.2 PreMETS platform operational and integration guidelines:** a report containing guidelines for the PreMETS platform to ensure that any interested party can replicate it.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be

presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

Start Month: 13
End Month: 21

Budget: 160.506,00€

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, Platform deployment.

Priority: Both deliverables are of medium priority and will be implemented at the second year of the project (M21). The successful finalisation of the platform as well as the integration of the work from WP2 and WP3, is an important deliverable and the fifth milestone of the project.

3.4.5 WP5: Work-based learning pilots

WP5 relates to OBJ5 of PreMETS (Pilot the training courses and the platform) and has as sub-objectives to define the pedagogical methodology for blended work-based learning (in company and via the PreMETS platform), recruit companies and trainees/apprentices for the PM pilots, implement 2 pilots of 3 months each and identify learning opportunities/improvements for the learners and trainers and institutionalize the work-based learning framework in the education providers' and industries' operations. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

- **D5.1 WBL Pilot 1:** regards the successful implementation of the 3-month pilot (PM in assembly line construction and transport, Romania).
- **D5.2 WBL Pilot 2:** regards the successful implementation of the 3-month pilot (PM in maritime operations).
- **D5.3 Mass virtual pilot:** regards the successful implementation of the virtual pilot. The PreMETS consortium under the coordination of EITM, will work on recruiting learners and trainers to register on the platform, undertake the courses and use the platform's tools. At least **500 registrations on the platform are expected**.
- **D5.4 Pilot reporting and evaluation:** a report covering lessons learned and suggestions/implications, assessing the effectiveness of the pilots especially with

regards to the collaboration, learning and impact on both the learners, trainers and stakeholders involved.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, their contribution to the achievement of the set targets (at least 50 in-person pilot participants and at least 500 virtual ones), the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

Start Month: 16

End Month: 33

Budget: 249.550,00€

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, not reaching the participant targets, COVID-19 risks, Data sharing reluctance

Priority: The deliverables are of low priority and will be implemented during the third year of the project. The successful implementation of both the physical and virtual pilots is the sixth milestone of the project that need to be implemented up to M33.

3.4.6 WP6: Monitoring and evaluation

WP6 ensures the effective and qualitative project content and activity development and has as sub-objectives to safeguard the compliance and format of the project's activities and outputs, to certify traceability of the project's actions and outcomes, to recognize and categorize potential problems or weaknesses in the project's actions and results with the purpose of remedy them, to review the project's results vis-à-vis expected impact and to assess the project's results per identified target-group. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

- **D6.1 Macro quality assurance plan:** an integrated report containing: Quality assurance plan (Task 6.1), VET/HEI quality assurance guidelines (Task 6.2) and the applied quality assurance guide (Task 6.3).

- **D6.2 Internal quality assurance report:** an integrated quality assurance report issued as a result of period quality controls of all the declared indicators. One interim report and one updated final report will be issued.
- **D6.3 External evaluation strategy:** an initial report explaining the external evaluation (present report).
- **D6.4 External evaluation report:** one interim and one updated final report will be issued as part of the external evaluation task.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

Start Month: 1
End Month: 36

Budget: 108.353,00€

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay.

Priority: D.6.1 and D.6.3 (present document) are of high priority and need to be implemented up to M3 and M6 accordingly. D.6.2 and 6.4 will be implemented later, during the second and third year of the project. Process and content quality standards implementation is an important deliverable and the seventh milestone of the project that need to be implemented up to M36.

3.4.7 WP7: Impact, Dissemination & Exploitation

WP7 aims to ensure that PreMETS reaches its impact and sustainability. Its sub-objectives are to maximise project visibility and its impact by demonstrating the scale of impact stemming from the project activities, to diffuse and multiply capacity and project excellence within and beyond the project consortium (EI-wide scale of impact), to identify synergies with other related projects and exchange knowledge in order to reuse, bind and exponentially facilitate the impact and result sustainability, to better facilitate the quadruple helix participatory engagement process and foresight exercises, to actively influence policy

and contribute to regional development, facilitate the achievement of the institutional, regional, national and international impact, formalize, institutionalize each component of PreMETS platform, and to devise a 10-year sustainability strategy for the PreMETS platform and secure the required resources (tangible, non-tangible). In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

- **D7.1 Communication and dissemination plan:** a report ensuring a well-coordinated dissemination and communication.
- **D7.2 Project visual identity pack:** including the Project website, Project logo and visual themes/guidelines and social media accounts setup.
- **D7.3 Mailing list:** a full (decentralized) mailing list with qualified contacts from each project partner (GDPR compliant) of **at least 10.000 contacts**.
- **D7.4 Newsletters & fliers:** **6 newsletters** in English (digital) with limited **printed version (600)** distributed to at least 10.000 contacts.
- **D7.5 Storytelling videos:** **6 videos** developed and disseminated to 20.000 contacts.
- **D7.6 Policy briefings:** **2 policy briefings** (15 pages each).
- **D7.7 Open day events:** **8 open day dissemination events** will be hosted by (each) partner.
- **D7.8 Media outlet events:** **At least 6 appearances** in TV/radio/conventional media will be produced.
- **D7.9 Impact measurement plan with a preliminary impact assessment:** a report introducing an impact measurement tool (methodology) that will build upon the quality, monitoring, dissemination, and progress activities even from the project implementation timeline in order to pave the way for impactful outcomes.
- **D7.10 PreMETS 10-year sustainability & commercialization plan:** a 6-step plan that would generate revenue while also improve the platform's offering.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, their contribution to the achievement of the set targets (10.000 contacts, 6 newsletters, 6 videos, 2 policy briefings, 8 open day events, 6 appearances in media), the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not

been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

Start Month: 1

End Month: 36

Budget: 277.927,00€

Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, platform deployment, limited impact of dissemination.

Priority: D.7.1, D.7.2 and D.7.9 are of high priority and need to be implemented up to M3. The 1st newsletter (D.7.4) should also be drafted and issued until M6.

The rest WP7 deliverables are of low priority, and they should be implemented until the end of the project. The last milestone of the project regards the preliminary impact indicators that finally achieved until M36.

A monitoring table which summarizes the examined indicators per WP and deliverable as well as the priority level of each output is presented in Annex A. This visualization will help external evaluator to also prioritize the indicators to those that need to be achieved in short-medium-long-term and suggest interventions if target values have not been met on time.

4. Conclusions

The report presents the evaluation methodology designed to ensure the delivery of high-quality outcomes aligned with the objectives of both Erasmus+ and the PreMETS project. This framework forms the cornerstone for developing external evaluation reports (both interim and final) for the PreMETS project.

Section 1: Introduction and Project Objectives

The first section introduces the project, outlining its objectives and goals in alignment with Erasmus+ guidelines and overarching objectives.

Section 2: Evaluation Approaches

It explores various evaluation approaches from academic and professional literature, each offering a comprehensive set of methods and processes for assessing project and program progress and success. A comparative analysis highlights the strengths and limitations of each approach, informing the selection of the most appropriate methodology for the PreMETS project. This choice was guided not only by the approaches' merits and drawbacks but also by the specific nature, context, and monitoring and evaluation objectives of the project.

Section 3: Detailed Evaluation Methodology

- 3.1 Evaluation Approach: A results-oriented approach was chosen, prioritizing monitoring and self-assessment of project progression towards defined outcomes and results. This method stands out for its ability to accurately track project success, facilitating early identification of issues or achievements and focusing on high-priority areas.
- 3.2 Evaluation Criteria and Tools: The section further identifies and analyses the evaluation criteria, indicators, and analytical tools. The process includes data collection and review, stakeholder interviews, qualitative scoring (using a traffic light system), and conclusions and recommendations drafted in line with the six DAC criteria (relevance, coherence, efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability), adapted specifically for the PreMETS project.
- 3.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): This subsection emphasizes KPIs defined in other project deliverables as essential for monitoring activity progress and evaluating success in achieving project objectives. These KPIs are designed to be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and timely, with clear target values.

- 3.4 Work Package Analysis: A preliminary assessment of each expected output/deliverable's significance, influence, priority level, and potential risk is conducted. The external evaluation will build on this analysis, comparing expected versus actual deliverables within the set timeframe and budget, examining deliverable quality, and identifying areas for improvement.

Conclusion: Strategy for Continuous Improvement

The developed strategy underscores the importance of continuous monitoring and self-assessment throughout the project lifecycle. Regular updates to KPIs are essential to ensure they remain relevant and attainable. Work Package analyses should be periodically revisited to reflect the evolving project dynamics, identifying new risks, and adjusting priorities. Finally, the external evaluation reports should go beyond assessing contractual deliverables against predefined criteria, also evaluating the quality of deliverables and their contribution to the overall project objectives.

5. References

- [1] Erasmus+ Programme Guide, Version 1 (2022): 24-11-2021: <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/erasmus-programme-guide>
- [2] European Commission, Better Regulation Guidelines, 2021, Brussels: http://ec.europa.eu/smart-regulation/guidelines/toc_guide_en.htm
- [3] European Commission, Mid-term evaluation of the Erasmus+ programme (2014-2020), 2018, Brussels, <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/eac/erasmus-plus/eval/swd-e-plus-mte.pdf>
- [4] EACEA, GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101108469 — PreMETS – ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO,2023
- [5] Gouédard P. (2021). Developing indicators to support the implementation of education policies (OECD Education Working Papers, No. 255). OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/paper/b9f04dd0-en>
- [6] Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2021, Applying Evaluation Criteria Thoughtfully, OECD Publishing <https://doi.org/10.1787/543e84ed-en>
- [7] Bakewell, O; Adams, J and Pratt, B (2003), Sharpening the Development Process; A practical guide to monitoring and evaluation. INTRAC, UK.
- [8] Guijt, I (2014). Participatory Approaches, Methodological Briefs: Impact Evaluation 5, UNICEF Office of Research, Florence.
- [9] Van Mierlo B. (2011). Approaches and methods for monitoring and evaluation, Wageningen University & Research eDepot.
- [10] European Institute of Innovation and Technology – EIT (2021). “MOTION capacity building: How to develop a theory of change for systems transformation?” <https://eit.europa.eu/library/motion-capacity-building-how-develop-theory-change-systems-transformation>
- [11] Weiss, C. H. (1995). Nothing as practical as good theory: Exploring theory-based evaluation for comprehensive community initiatives for children and families. In J. Connell, A. Kubisch, L. B. Schorr, & C. H. Weiss (Eds.), *New approaches to evaluating community 30 initiatives: Volume 1, concepts, methods, and contexts* (pp. 65-92). New York, NY: Aspen Institute.
- [12] White, H (2009). Theory-Based Impact Evaluation: Principles and practice. Working paper no. 3. International Initiative for Impact Evaluation, June 2009.

- [13] Stern, E; Stame, N; Mayne, J; Forss, K; Davies, R and Befani, B (2012). Broadening the Range of Designs and Methods for Impact Evaluations: Report of a study commissioned by the Department for International Development (DFID). Working paper 38, April 2012.
- [14] ActionAid (2016). How to... Select a Methodological Approach for the Evaluation. Evaluation Technical Briefing Note, #7. ActionAid, UK.
- [15] Rogers, P (2012). Introduction to Impact Evaluation. Impact Evaluation Notes no. 1. InterAction, March 2012.
- [16] Perrin, B (2012). Linking Monitoring and Evaluation to Impact Evaluation. Impact Evaluation Notes no. 2. InterAction, April 2012.
- [17] Stern, E (2015). Impact Evaluation: A guide for commissioners and managers. BOND, May 2015

ANNEX A: LIST OF INDICATORS AND PRIORITY LEVEL PER WP

WP	DELIVERABLE	DUE DATE	PRIORITY	INDICATORS RELATED & TARGET VALUE
WP1	D1.1	1	High	-
	D.1.2	1	High	-
WP2	D.2.1	3	High	-
	D.2.2	12	Medium	✓ Number of the PM training modules (6)
	D.2.3	12	Medium	-
	D.2.4	12	Medium	-
	D.2.5	12	Medium	✓ Number of train-the-trainers modules (8)
WP3	D.3.1	12	Medium	-
	D.3.2	15	Medium	-
WP4	D.4.1	21	Medium	✓ % of trustworthiness in e-learning platforms (>45%)
	D.4.2	21	Medium	✓ % of interest in e-learning platforms (>20%)
WP5	D.5.1	24	Medium	✓ Number of certified learners via micro credentials (500)
	D.5.2	27	Low	
	D.5.3	33	Low	
	D.5.4	33	Low	✓ Number of trained learners in PM (1000) Number of trained trainers in PM (250)
				✓ Number of companies engaged (20) ✓ Number of universities and VET centers adopting PreMETS (50)
WP6	D.6.1	3	High	-
	D.6.2	36	Low	-
	D.6.3	6	High	-
	D.6.4	36	Low	-
WP7	D.7.1	3	High	-
	D.7.2	3	High	✓ Number of website visitors (5000)
	D.7.3	36	Low	✓ Number of contacts (10000)
	D.7.4	36	Low	✓ Number of newsletters (6) and printed material produced (600)
	D.7.5	36	Low	✓ Number of videos produced (6)
	D.7.6	36	Low	-
	D.7.7	36	Low	✓ Number of open day events organized (8)

WP	DELIVERABLE	DUE DATE	PRIORITY	INDICATORS RELATED & TARGET VALUE
	D.7.8	36	Low	✓ Number of appearances in TV/radio/conventional media (6)
	D.7.9	36	Low	-
	D.7.10	36	Low	-

ANNEX B: INTERNAL REPORTS' CODIFICATION

PreMETS Internal Reports Codification (Document ID): CERTH/HIT6.6_1.DOC: first revision of report in Task 6.6 of CERTH/HIT